

A Study on the Quality of Customer Service in Insurance Companies in India

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Introduction :

Customer service and the customer experience are becoming an important competitive differentiator in the insurance industry. To establish a successful relationship between insurers and customers, companies must focus on meeting consumer demands during each phase of the customer journey. It is also necessary to identify the key success factors in insurance industry, such as customer satisfaction, intense competition and increase in the market share. Insurance companies in India offer a wide variety of products and supplementary services, streamlining sales and distribution channels along with targeted advertising and marketing campaigns. With increased globalization and presence of a large number of players in the market, the customer relationship and satisfaction is in danger of being proved incomplete.

History of Insurance in India :

In India, insurance has a deep-rooted history. It finds mention in the writings of Manu (*Manusmrithi*), Yagnavalkya (*Dharmasastra*) and Kautilya (*Arthasastra*). The writings talk in terms of pooling of resources that could be re-distributed in times of calamities such as fire, floods, epidemics and famine. This was probably a pre-cursor to modern day insurance. Ancient Indian history has preserved the earliest traces of insurance in the form of marine trade loans and carriers' contracts. Insurance in India has evolved over time heavily drawing from other countries, England in particular.

Important milestones in the Indian Life Insurance Business :

- ✓ **1912** : The Indian Life Assurance Companies Act came into force for regulating the life insurance business.
- ✓ **1928** : The Indian Insurance Companies Act was enacted for enabling the government to collect statistical information on both life and non-life insurance businesses.
- ✓ **1938** : The earlier legislation consolidated the Insurance Act with the aim of safeguarding the interests of the insuring public.
- ✓ **1956** : 245 Indian and foreign insurers and provident societies were taken over by the Central Government and they got nationalized. LIC was formed by an Act of Parliament, viz. LIC Act, 1956. It started off with a capital of 5 crore and that too from the Government of India.

Important milestones in the Indian General Insurance Business :

- ✓ **1907** : The Indian Mercantile Insurance Ltd. was set up which was the first company of its type to transact all general insurance business.
- ✓ **1957** : General Insurance Council, an arm of the Insurance Association of India, framed a code of conduct for guaranteeing fair conduct and sound business patterns.
- ✓ **1968** : The Insurance Act improved for regulating investments and set minimal solvency levels and the Tariff Advisory Committee was set up.

- ✓ **1972** : The General Insurance Business (Nationalization) Act, 1972 nationalized the general insurance business in India. It came into effect from 1st January 1973.

Significance of Customer Service in Insurance Sector :

1. Improve trust and information exchange :

In the Insurance sector, good customer service generates satisfied or delighted customers and it leads to increased compliance, improved information exchange, improved relationships, increased trust and decreased workloads or costs.

2. Save money and increases profit :

In the Insurance sector, good customer service generates customer loyalty, which produces increased revenues and reduced costs.

3. Competition and technological upgradation :

Consumers are becoming more sophisticated in their requirements and are increasingly demanding higher standards of services. Therefore, interest in managing the services through customer service is considerably high in insurance sectors. It requires setting customer service objectives in terms of relative importance of customer service element.

Customer service in Insurance Sector - Action Plan :

1. Identify the target customer :

Begin identifying the target customers by considering the point of purchase, point of service delivery or receipt, and point of consumption. Cluster or segment target customers based on their common behaviors, knowing that targeting the wrong customers can have adverse effects on the organization. Determine the priorities of various clusters of customers, knowing that the capabilities of the organization are crucial in addressing these priorities.

2. Determine what customers wants :

Determine how the target customers prioritize their “wants.” Generally, customers want convenience, quality products and services, variety or selection, low prices, and protection or security. However, each organization must identify what is most important to its customers. Weigh how important the customer-identified “wants” are to the organization.

3. Establish an organizational culture supportive of customer service :

Utilizing the information gathered, establish the company's customer-focused vision. The vision statement should be simple and may also identify what the company does not want to be. Live up to what is promised by concurrently developing and applying externally and internally oriented strategic service concepts that reflect the vision. If the organization does not implement both internally and externally oriented service strategies consistent with the vision, the organization will have good intentions but poor customer service.

4. Implement an Externally Oriented Strategic Service Concept :

The externally oriented strategic service concept establishes how the organization's service is designed, marketed, and delivered to target customers. Take into account the costs of providing services and ways to minimize those costs while implementing quality control. The service concept must be developed with the frontline worker at its center.

5. Implement an Internally Oriented Strategic Service Concept :

The internally oriented strategic service concept establishes how the organization's internal processes will support the customer-focused vision. The premise behind the internally oriented strategic service concept is "capable workers who are well trained and fairly compensated provide better service, need less supervision, and are much more likely to stay on the job.

Conclusion :

In insurance industry, the insurer-customer relationship is a valuable competitive differentiator throughout the entire customer journey from the initial consultation through support and claims. To put customers front and center every step of the way, insurers need to proactively communicate during the information phase, focus on personalizing interactions with customers on diverse channels during the purchase phase and create a blend between personal contact and digital tools to elevate support and claims services. To attract and retain customers, insurers must actively seek out opportunities to innovate their customer service approach to address customers' needs and drive positive customer experiences during every touch point along the customer journey.

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